

Achieving gradual failure in hybrid composite laminates in bending

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Composites are brittle!

- Lack of Ductility is a serious disadvantage for composite materials

Video: Catastrophic failure of carbon fibre tubes

Pseudo-ductile hybrid composites

High strain material

Low strain material

Hybrid

Gradual failure in hybrids - background

- Tension
 - Uni-Direction (UD): Developed an analytical model, damage mode map, and several successful experimental results
 - Quasi-Isotropic (QI): pseudo-ductility in all fibre directions
 - Open Hole and sharp notches: notch insensitive composites
 - High strain rates: gradual failure and fragmentation achieved
- Compression
 - Uni-Direction (UD): Carbon fibre fragmentation in high modulus carbon fibre hybrids
- Fatigue
 - Uni-Direction (UD): Achieved infinite/long fatigue life of hybrids if max strain is less than 80% of knee point strain.
 - Quasi-Isotropic of un-notched and open hole hybrids

Bending in this paper

In this conference

Some of the papers are listed in the reference slide at the end.

Failure modes in bending

- Compressive side failure
 - Mostly due to fibre instability

- Tensile side failure
 - Fibre failure

Avoiding compressive failure

- Gradual failure and instability are incompatible

- Decision: Using s-glass on the compressive side to minimise the compressive stress on the carbon layer and avoid any compressive failure.

Designing the hybrid for tension load

- We know how to achieve pseudo-ductility under pure tension force.

Damage modes in hybrids under pure tension

- Damage may develop in 4 different ways:

M Jalalvand, G Czél, MR Wisnom, 2015

Damage mode map

- A simple and accurate tool for optimal UD hybrid configurations.

Example a pseudo-ductile hybrid in tension

G Czél, M Jalalvand, MR Wisnom, 2016

Material selection

- Combination of three fibres are selected:
 - S-glass for the compressive side
 - T1000 with 2.2% failure strain as the High strain material on the tensile side
 - M55 with 0.8% failure strain as the Low strain material on the tensile side

Prepreg Material	Elastic Modulus [GPa]	Tensile Failure Strain [%]	Compression Failure Strain [%]	Cured ply thickness [mm]
S-Glass/epoxy	45.7	3.98	2.33	0.155
T1000/epoxy	143.3	2.2	1.1	0.0323
M55/epoxy	280.0	0.8	0.26	0.0305

- Compressive failure strains are much lower than the tensile ones.

Damage mode map of T1000/M55

Expected stress-strain curves

Final layup

- layup 1:

[S-Glass₇/M55/T1000/(T1000/M55/T1000)₁₇/T1000]

repetition unit

- Layup 2:

[S-Glass₇/T1000/M55/ T1000₂/(T1000₂/M55/T1000₂)₁₀]

repetition unit

Bending moment required to fail each layer

- Required bending moment to fail each layer is shown by a **blue dot** for tensile and **red dot** for compressive failure.
- Neutral axis position is shown by green circle.
- Numbers show the order of failure. This shows the first 4 layers to fail are M55 under compression and then M55 in tension.

Experiments

- 4-point bending to get pure bending response.

- Strain gauge to monitor tensile strains

The beam at final loading point

- The bending deflection was so large that the loading fixture needed to be changed so that the extra displacement could be applied.

Load-displacements

- Initial non-linear curve due to fragmentation and non-linear geometry
- Progressive layer failure / delamination after the plateau

Failure mechanism

1. Low strain material fragmentation

2. High strain material failure

3. Instantaneous delamination

4. Fragmentation of the inner low strain material and repeat of steps 1 to 4 again

Brush-like failure

- Specimen with huge amount of distributed damage after unloading

Conclusions

- Unstable failure on compressive side successfully avoided
- Gradual fragmentation of the low strain material achieved
- High strain material failure followed by delamination of the surface hybrid block led to gradual failure
- Distributed failure with high energy absorption achieved

References

- M Jalalvand, G Czél, MR Wisnom, 2015, Damage analysis of pseudo-ductile thin-ply UD hybrid composites—a new analytical method, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 69, 83-93
- G Czél, M Jalalvand, MR Wisnom, 2016, Design and characterisation of advanced pseudo-ductile unidirectional thin-ply carbon/epoxy–glass/epoxy hybrid composites, *Composite Structures* 143, 362-370
- M Fotouhi, J Fuller, M Longana, M Jalalvand, MR Wisnom, 2019, The high strain rate tension behaviour of pseudo-ductile high performance thin ply composites, *Composite Structures* 215, 365-376
- M Fotouhi, M Jalalvand, MR Wisnom, 2018, Notch insensitive orientation-dispersed pseudo-ductile thin-ply carbon/glass hybrid laminates, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 110, 29-44
- M Fotouhi, P Suwarta, R Jenkin, M Jalalvand, M Wisnom, 2019, Fatigue behaviour of un-notched and open-hole quasi-isotropic pseudo-ductile thin-ply carbon/glass hybrid laminates, *ICCM 22*, Melbourne

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